

SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Since independence, Kazakhstan has been implementing many programs and prerequisites for its development. It is known that the economic, social, cultural and political development of the country is carried out on the basis of ongoing reforms and laws. Kazakhstan has overcome the 20-year threshold. New prospects have opened up before our country. However, for several years now, the world has been troubled. The crisis has not been overcome at the global level, and the world community is in a pressurized turbulent situation.

The modern world is interconnected at an extreme level with all its pluses and minuses. This is a reality that all countries must reckon with. It has a lot to do with all the big, medium and small countries. All this requires the state to implement a piecemeal social policy. At the same time, it is necessary to always keep social problems under control and constantly update them.

Over the years of independence, a solid foundation of a social state has been laid in Kazakhstan. Objectively, Kazakhstan approached the level of quality of social development of the middle European countries. The way of life of Kazakhstanis is growing steadily. But the most important question is how effectively our country uses the fruits of stability and prosperity. It is very important for Kazakhstan to find an effective balance between economic income and the provision of public goods.

Keywords: social problems, alcoholism, piracy, criminality, unemployment, corruption, suicide, terrorism, political situation, government, society, political situation, young people.

1.1 Theoretical aspects of social problems in Kazakhstan

Social problems should not be postponed. And this, in turn, requires answers to questions about what Kazakhstan's society should look like in the conditions of global instability, in the conditions of the new century in order to withstand global storms.

As the social, economic, political situation in society and the country changes, the importance of maintaining political stability and social harmony increases. Political stability and social harmony are values that are mandatory for the population at any stage of Kazakhstan. Without stability and harmony, no reforms will be implemented. First of all, the population needs sustainable development. He needs not only the authorities, but also the people. When looking at social studies, 80% of the population of Kazakhstan notes the importance of political stability in society. It can be said that the goals and objectives of the population as a whole revolve around this value.

1.2 The aims and objectives of social problems in Kazakhstan

What are our unrealized reserves and opportunities? What else should be done to make social policy sustainable and creative?

During this work, we will simplify the social problems in Kazakhstan and the political situation in our country and answer the above questions.

- In the course of the task that we are investigating, to determine the types of social problems in Kazakhstan.

- Delve into each problem in detail and attach importance to it in society.

- By conducting social surveys and statistical data, we find solutions to these social problems

1.3 Objects of the research of social problems

Social problems and problems in the country can be divided into several parts. All important areas - education, health care, culture, sports, the activities of civil society institutions, etc. - are regulated by special legislative acts. Now all social problems in our country can be classified according to the following problems. These include: a small number of middle-class people, alcoholism, piracy, homelessness, unemployment, high mortality rates, environmental pollution, the state of the disabled, corruption, drug addiction, violations of children's rights, the lower birth rate, the state of the elderly, suicide, religious dissent, terrorism, prostitution, etc. We will talk more about the impact of these problems on the society and social life of Kazakhstan.

1.4 Characteristics of social problems

The first problem is alcoholism. According to research by the World Health Organization, Kazakhstan is among the top ten in the world in terms of the large number of people suffering from alcoholism. Of course, this is an alarming situation. Looking at this, there is reason to worry about the future of the sovereign country. This is because, according to experts, alcoholic beverages not only poison the human body, but also cause various diseases. According to statistics, about 28 thousand people in the country say goodbye to the world every year due to binge drinking, exacerbating diseases such as liver, cardiovascular, stomach ulcers, brain stroke.

Special studies have proven that the majority of children born in families with alcoholics have poor health and low ability. For example, French doctors conducted a study of 57 children born into ten alcoholic families. As a result, 25 children died in infancy, 5 chil-

dren suffered from cholera, and 5 from severe brain tumors. It was also known that 12 children were born mentally retarded, and only the remaining 10 children were relatively healthy.

After such a situation, there is no way not to look at the future of innocent babies born in a family with an alcoholic, but with suspicion. It is especially sad that in our country, which adheres to the principle "the health of the generation is the health of the nation", today the number of young people who are addicted to alcohol increases every year. According to domestic neurologists, over the past three or four years, the number of children turning to alcoholism has increased 10 times.

According to statistics, the volume of vodka and wine products sold in Kazakhstan for a year is 12 liters per person per capita. The results of an international examination suggest that if this figure exceeds 8 liters, the future of such a country is at risk.

According to experts, a third of those who suffer from alcoholism are those who suffer from psychological disorders.

The second problem is piracy, criminality. The number of criminals is growing in Kazakhstan. Official figures indicate that most of the criminals are unemployed. Crime among women and minor children has also increased. According to the statistics agency of Kazakhstan, in January-July 2011, the number of criminals increased. During this time, 97,692 crimes were registered in the Republic. That is, more than 19,550 crimes were registered (25% more) compared to the same period last year. Material damage from committing a crime-158,516.3 million tenge. Of these, 61.6% are accounted for by the economic sphere, and 25.3% are related to private property. Law enforcement agencies of the country detected 47,620 violations. This is 2.5 percent less than last year. 30,227 people were brought to criminal responsibility (8.8% less than last year). 91.2 percent of crimes were committed by people who went to such a case for the first time. The share of repeat offenders is 8.8 percent. And 78.6% of crimes were committed by the unemployed. Evidence that crime is a social phenomenon is that the citizens who committed the crime are mostly unemployed. And their number, although small, is constantly increasing. If in 2006 their share was 72.7%, in 2007-73.3%, in 2008-2009-74%, in 2010-75%. The inability to find a place in life also pushes a person to commit criminal acts. According to my own calculations, over the past five years, more than 370 thousand people (2.3% of the total population) have committed crimes in Kazakhstan for the first time.

The main reasons for the increase in crime are unresolved socio – economic problems, lack of ideological and educational work. Now the traditional oriental model of respect for women and children is being ignored. For this reason, crimes against women increased by 147.5%, and crimes against minor children-by 125%. In general, three-quarters of all crimes were committed against women. Real cash incomes of the population decreased by 1.4% in July 2011 compared to the previous year. According to the International Labor Organization, in August 2011, 461.2 thousand people were unemployed, and unemployment was 5.3%.

Various life situations, housing problems, unemployment, lack of support and prospects, dead ends push a person to the criminal path.

If we talk about the problem of unemployment in Kazakhstan. An important and complex problem is the use of labor resources in accordance with the new requirements associated with the formation of a new economic system in sovereign Kazakhstan, the transition to market relations. Especially in the future, due to some aggravation of demographic processes and the increasing requirements for the quality of labor in the world competitive environment, the relevance of this problem will continue to increase. In Kazakhstan, unemployment in the labor market - employment of labor resources, the formation of a labor market in accordance with the requirements of today is one of the most important issues that await its solution. According to the statistics agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the total number of unemployed people in Kazakhstan in 2011 amounted to 473.0 thousand people, which is 23.6 thousand people (4.7%) less than last year. The unemployment rate is 5.4% (in 2010 – 5.8%). The share of unemployed men is 43.3%, women– 56.7%. Last year, the total number of unemployed young people (15-24 years old) was 12.2%, or 57.9 thousand people. Unemployment is the No. 1 social disease that threatens the security of the nation, regardless of State. It is clear that the root of crime and poverty, prostitution and poverty, comes down to unemployment.

For any civilized society, the fight against corruption is one of the most pressing questions. There is no doubt that corruption is a threat to national security, negating the initiative and achievements of the destruction of the state from the inside. Therefore, one of the main priorities of the state policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan is the fight against this evil.

The fight against corruption is one of the most serious problems of our country today. It is clear that, being a great social tragedy, it greatly worries any of the countries in the world that are not alike in terms of political development. The history of the fight against corruption in independent Kazakhstan can be divided into four stages. The first stage – 1992-1998. The initial stage of the fight against corruption and the formation of a regulatory framework. The second stage – 1998-2000. The emergence of anti-corruption legislation as the main legal and methodological basis for the fight against corruption.

The third stage – 2001-2004. Formation of a systematic approach to solving the problems of combating corruption. The fourth stage is from February 2005. Kazakhstan's fight against corruption in the context of rapid economic, social and political modernization.

In 2011, 50 corruption cases were exposed. The damage was 256.4 million. tenge. 49 cases of corruption crimes were sent to the court.

The most common types of corruption crimes are theft of budget funds (19), official forgery (16), bribery (8), abuse of official authority (5). About half of all identified corruption cases were committed in Aktau, 40% in Zhanaozen, and the remaining 12% in other districts.

On corruption: 3 criminal cases were initiated against rural akims, 16 against employees of state institutions, 7 against state-owned enterprises. On behalf of the head of state and the chairman of the agency, the operational-service staff of the Department of financial police in Mangystau region is aimed at ensuring the protection of the legal rights and interests of citizens and entrepreneurs.

As the head of state noted, "the fight against corruption is not only persistent measures to punish criminals, it is a whole complex of daily work of the state and society." Therefore, every citizen of the Republic of Kazakhstan is obliged to prevent corruption. Corruption has no place in our society. It is possible to effectively counter this phenomenon only by uniting the efforts of all institutions of civil society, using international experience and all means to stop this disease so that it does not worsen further.

All the above-mentioned social problems are currently being studied, and there are those that, in turn, find or do not find solutions. However, since I am a member of a social group, a future young specialist, a young person, I would like to dwell on the problems of youth in general. The number of young people, depending on their social status, can be expressed based on statistical data. According to the 2005 World Report on the situation of youth, the number of young people (between 15 and 24 years old) increased from 1.02 billion to 1.15 billion people in 2005 compared to 1995. It turns out that today young people make up 18% of the world's population.

Based on the opinions of scientists studying issues related to young people, they have many problems that need to be solved. Of these, five are especially distinguished. As a word, we would like to note that due to the lack of research on the problem of youth in Kazakhstan, in most cases we will have to rely on the data of Russian specialists.

The first of them is "where do I live?" the problem. There are several facets to this, that is, the issue of an apartment. First, young people are not at all times and everywhere a secured part of society. After all, they are a separate class in a society that has just begun to exist, living mainly at the expense of the income of their parents. And parents, due to their views on life or material conditions, are not always able to optimally solve the question of whether a child, a young family needs their own apartment after marriage. In many cases, parents do not even have the ability to meet the requirements of their children. Even young people have no money. And if they want to get a loan, on the one hand, because they do not have a stable job and a large income, banks cannot provide them with loans, on the other hand, even if they find a way to get a loan, young people cannot afford to pay for loans at a very high rate.

The second problem "where and how do I study?" "I don't know," he said. Without higher education, professional training, it is impossible to find a job with good earnings. Therefore, the majority of young people, or rather those who are thinking about their own tomorrow, try to continue their education even after school. But even at the same time, the question of money goes ahead. After all, in order to enter a

university for free, you need to be a born talent. And such a feature was not written on the forehead of one of the two. Even if everyone was gifted, due to limited grants, a certain part of them would have to study for a fee. Where does a young man who is just starting his life path find such finances? In this regard, it is necessary to recognize that the opinion that only those who fail the exam or test deserve to continue their studies is also a negative attitude. In order to become a good specialist, a business organizer in the future, it is not even necessary to stand out by passing the tests for 4 and 5. After all, it is known that any test questions cannot reveal all the abilities of a person. If you want, it is quite possible that some who fail the tests and successfully complete their studies later turn out to be completely incompetent when it comes to practical work. Here we are talking about the possibility of many entrepreneurs and talents among young people who, due to the inability to pass such tests as exams and tests, did not have enough access to higher education, or rather, a diploma.

Third problem "where do I rest?" "I don't know," he said. It is natural for young people to look for places to have fun and spend time. In any era, this was considered a very important issue for the younger generation. This is because it is easy for young people who are bored, unable to find a way to spend their free time with benefit, to fall on the wrong path. Crimes such as drug addiction, alcoholism, theft, fights are caused by the same reasons, impressionable and feverish behavior of young people "unable to fit both hands in front of them".

The fourth problem is "how do I live?" it's called. Here we are talking about income. Even with a diploma, a young specialist without experience is unlikely to be able to get a high-paying job. For example, those who are invited to a good job require that they have at least 5 years of experience. And it is clear that young people want to live freely, seeing all the delights of life. In addition, he should also think about the side of promotion in the service. "I don't know," he said. Especially in the era of the market, when the principle that everyone should see their own day is emerging, these problems are becoming the most difficult to solve.

The last problem is "what goals should be pursued?" there is a dead end around the question. Russian experts believe that today's young people do not have clear life guidelines, as happened with their parents. After all, now there are no common goals that can be formed at the state level, nor a powerful propaganda machine that will mobilize the public to do so. Our fathers and mothers had knowledge of the laws of society, they knew in advance what goals it was possible to achieve and which ones were impossible, Russian experts believe. Most likely, it is reasonable to understand that this was also carried out by the Communist Party, which aimed to unite the people of the whole country only around itself. Modern youth does not have such opportunities. After all, now there are many parties, associations and various currents in the country. In addition, today's youth has seen and learned from the experience of foreign parties that

today's parties are created not to "establish communism", as before, but to compete for power. Therefore, the younger generation, who have not yet found their place in life, is not very interested in the crowded political parties. Many studies around the world have found that young people are less willing to engage in politics. But they are forced to feel their helplessness and helplessness in front of them, seeing the wealthy and commanding brothers, with whom only they decide everything. Such a vision infuriates young people and pushes them to some random actions.

CONCLUSION OF THE 1ST CHAPTER

All these social problems and conditions are the most important problems of our society. To solve these social problems in society and further develop our society, various events are organized, reforms are carried out, laws are introduced, programs are developed. These are just a few of the listed problems. We didn't stop. Speaking about what measures are being taken by the state, non-governmental

organizations, social funds, etc. to address topical issues. In general, there are many programs implemented in the country.

Based on the sources of information, I understand that social problems should be solved in the state not individually, but in a complex way. This program and reforms should be implemented in the state, region, district, village. Only in this case will we be able to solve all social problems and increase the middle class. Every citizen of Kazakhstan should contribute to the social development of Kazakhstan. I believe that every person should look to the future not with fear, but with high hopes. This is because the individual is one member of society, the creator and formator of society. For the social development of Kazakhstan, every citizen of Kazakhstan must make his contribution.

II ANALYTICAL SELECTION OF Social problems in Kazakhstan

2.1 Analysis of methods of social problems in Kazakhstan

Do you drink alcoholic beverages?

How often?

Are you capable of stealing?

- I can only steal if my life depends on it
- I can steal, but only at work, from the state or the "owner"
- I can steal if something is bad
- Under no circumstances did I take will not take someone else's

Have you ever stolen?

- Yes, unwittingly (for example, accidentally taking someone else's thing with you)
- Yes, but insignificant things, such as forks from a restaurant for your collection, or a towel from a hotel
- Yes, constantly, this is my main source of income
- No, I have never taken someone else's

What do you think is the unemployment rate in Kazakhstan today?

- High
- Normal (natural)
- Low

What, in your opinion, are the main causes of youth unemployment?

Are there any unemployed people in your family?

2.2 Modern technologies for solving problems

Corruption: Technologies such as blockchain and big data analytics can be used to create more transparent and accountable systems for tracking government spending and identifying corrupt practices. Additionally, social media can be used to raise awareness of corruption and mobilize citizens to demand greater transparency and accountability from government officials.

Suicide: Digital mental health platforms, such as chatbots and teletherapy services, can provide accessible and affordable mental health support for those who may be struggling with suicidal thoughts. Social media and online support groups can also provide a community of support and resources for those in need.

Terrorism: Technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning can be used to analyze and identify potential terrorist threats, allowing for more effective prevention and intervention strategies. Additionally, social media monitoring and analysis can help identify extremist content and prevent its spread.

Unemployment: Online job matching platforms, such as LinkedIn and Indeed, can help connect job seekers with potential employers, while also providing tools for career development and training. Additionally, e-learning platforms can provide accessible and affordable educational opportunities to help individuals acquire new skills and qualifications.

Criminality and robbery: Surveillance technologies, such as CCTV cameras and facial recognition

software, can be used to deter criminal activity and identify suspects. Smart city technologies, such as intelligent lighting and sensor networks, can also improve public safety by making public spaces more visible and responsive to potential threats.

Alcoholism: Digital health technologies, such as wearable sensors and mobile apps, can be used to monitor alcohol consumption and provide real-time feedback and support to those who may be struggling with addiction. Online support groups and teletherapy services can also provide accessible and confidential support to those in need.

Political situation: Social media and online news platforms can provide alternative sources of information and foster greater political engagement and dialogue. Additionally, digital democracy platforms, such as e-voting systems and online citizen engagement tools, can provide more opportunities for citizen participation in the political process.

2.3 Description of social problems in Kazakhstan

Corruption: Corruption is a significant problem in Kazakhstan, with reports of bribery and other corrupt practices being common in government and business. This has led to a lack of transparency and accountability in government spending, hindering economic development and undermining public trust in government institutions.

Suicide: Suicide is a growing problem in Kazakhstan, particularly among young people. Factors contributing to this issue include social and economic pressures, mental health issues, and a lack of access to affordable and effective mental health services.

Terrorism: Terrorism and extremist activities are a concern in Kazakhstan, with the country facing threats from both domestic and international groups. The government has taken steps to prevent and combat terrorism, but the threat remains.

Unemployment: Unemployment is a significant problem in Kazakhstan, particularly among young people and in rural areas. This has led to social and economic inequality and contributed to brain drain as many skilled workers seek employment opportunities abroad.

Criminality and robbery: Crime rates in Kazakhstan have been rising in recent years, with reports of theft, burglary, and other property crimes being common. Organized crime syndicates are also a concern, particularly in urban areas.

Alcoholism: Alcoholism is a significant problem in Kazakhstan, with high levels of alcohol consumption contributing to a range of health and social issues. This includes domestic violence, traffic accidents, and a range of health issues such as liver disease and cancer.

Political situation: Kazakhstan has been criticized for its lack of political freedom and human rights abuses. The ruling party has been in power for decades, and opposition parties and media outlets are often restricted or shut down. There are also concerns about corruption and electoral fraud.

CONCLUSION OF THE 2nd CHAPTER

In conclusion, Kazakhstan faces a range of social problems that require innovative and effective solutions. Corruption, suicide, terrorism, unemployment, criminality, robbery, alcoholism, and the political situation are among the most pressing issues facing the country. The use of modern technologies such as blockchain, big data analytics, artificial intelligence, and machine learning can be effective in addressing many of these issues. Additionally, improving access to affordable and effective mental health services, educational opportunities, and employment opportunities can help to address some of the root causes of these social prob-

lems. To truly address these issues, however, it will require a comprehensive and sustained effort from government, civil society, and the private sector to work together to create a more just, equitable, and prosperous society for all Kazakhstanis.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the first chapter emphasizes the importance of addressing social problems in Kazakhstan through a comprehensive and sustained effort, implemented at various levels of society. This includes programs, reforms, and laws introduced by the government, as well as contributions from non-governmental organizations and social funds. Every citizen of Kazakhstan has a role to play in the social development of the country, and should look towards the future with hope and a commitment to making a positive impact. The second chapter highlights the specific social problems facing Kazakhstan, including corruption, suicide, terrorism, unemployment, criminality, robbery, alcoholism, and the political situation. The chapter emphasizes the potential for modern technologies such as blockchain, big data analytics, artificial intelligence, and machine learning to help address these issues. Additionally, access to affordable mental health services, education, and employment opportunities are identified as key factors in addressing the root causes of these social problems. The chapter concludes that collaboration between government, civil society, and the private sector is necessary to create a more just, equitable, and prosperous society for all Kazakhstanis.

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